

PoI – Points of Interest in Destinations

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AIR Brief Reports

Kernergebnisse

- Points of Interest (PoI) are geographical locations worth visiting.
- Experiential PoI (E-PoI) are points of attraction.
- Functional PoI (F-PoI) are points that assist in visiting E-PoI.
- Measurements at an F-PoI can be used as a proxy for visitor numbers at an E-PoI if there is a strong relationship between the two.

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Date: 15 March 2023

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Introduction

In the context of (digital) tourism visitor management, points of interest (PoI) play an important role as points of attraction for visitors and thus also as potential locations for visitor measurements (Schmücker et al., 2022). At the same time, many tourism databases use “PoI” fields as a matter of course in destination management practice. We suspect that there is an intuitive notion of what PoI are in research and practice. A clear definition and categorisation in the context of visitor management is missing so far.

Literature Review

First mentions of the term “point of interest” or “PoI” in the tourism context can be found in the late 1990s. Wall (1997) suggests points (museums, theatres etc.), lines (coasts, routes etc.) and areas (protected areas etc.) as possible distinguishing features of attractions. In subsequent years, PoI are defined as “monuments and streets” (Crainic et al., 2004), “a hotel, a restaurant” (Burigat et al., 2005, p. 214) or “museums and their catalogues, monumental buildings and historical information associated with them, restaurants and their menus, shops and their current promotions, hotels with reservation services, digitised old postcards, etc.” (van Setten et al., 2004). Braunhofer et al. (2013) consider a “place of interest” to be simply the destination of a visit. Yilmaz et al. (2017) define a point of interest as a “particular location point that is useful or interesting for people, such as restaurants, museums, parks and hotels”. A very simple yet comprehensive definition of point of interest is “a specific point location that someone may find useful” (Xu et al., 2018). In current literature, points of interest have the following characteristics: they are locatable, geographically definable, accessible, visited by tourists and attractive (Padrón-Ávila & Hernández-

Martín, 2022). Points of interest are understood as “specific place[s] within a tourism destination where a significant number of tourists stop. The reason for stopping must be their interest in enjoying one or more elements that can be found within that place. This means that places where visits to them are obligatory or necessary are not points of interest”. (Padrón-Ávila & Hernández-Martín, 2022, p. 526).

The abbreviation “PoI” is sometimes also used for “Point of Information” (in distinction to Point of Sale, Horner & Swarbrooke, 2006, p. 214) or for “Potential of Interest”. Potential of Interest is “the sightseeing potential of each place in a tourist area, which is estimated from data about locations where previous visitors have found something impressive” (Kurata, 2012).

Methods to define PoI

Three methods can be distinguished for defining PoI:

1. Definition based on obvious categories: For car drivers, petrol stations or charging stations are of interest, therefore all petrol stations or charging stations can be defined as PoI for car drivers. For overnight guests, overnight accommodation is usually of interest, therefore all overnight accommodation could be defined as PoI for overnight guests.
2. determination by experts: whether a certain place is “of interest” can be determined, for example, by the Destination Management Organisation (DMO) or other persons with expertise. In practice, a set of categories has been established that are regularly classified as PoI (e.g. hotel, museum, etc.).

3. Determination from the customer's point of view: some studies have attempted to infer the PoI status of certain places from digital reports on social media (Rae et al., 2012; Yilmaz et al., 2017).

Definition

In the context of visitor management, we use the second method to define PoIs and describe the use of the term in this framework. Based on the definition of Xu et al. (2018, "a specific point location that someone may find useful"), we define a tourist PoI as follows:

A tourist point of interest (PoI) is a geographical location worth visiting in the context of tourist travel.

We thus exclude immaterial places or purely virtual points that do not exist in geographical reality (e.g. Pokémons) from the definition, because in the context of visitor management we try to influence the real movement in space. However, the digital (virtual) *representation* of geographical locations is of high importance for visitor management, because without a digital representation, digital visitor management is not possible.

PoI are therefore geographical locations whose position and extent can be clearly defined by coordinates. Accordingly, points, areas (polygons) or lines (polylines) can represent PoI.

A core concept in the definition is “worth visiting”. To what extent a place is worth visiting depends on

1. the characteristics of the place (accessibility etc.),
2. the characteristics of the travellers (wishes, needs, planning) and
3. the context of the specific trip (e.g. holiday or business trip).

This makes it clear that a place is not a PoI *per se*, but that the perspective of the users and the context is necessary.

Categories of PoI: E-PoI and F-PoI

PoI are divided into different content categories in destination practice, such as

- attractions,
- landscapes,
- cultural places,
- adventure facilities,
- gastronomy,
- accommodation,
- mobility,
- routes, tracks and tours,
- meeting locations.

These PoIs are worth visiting because they can fulfil a desire for an experience (Schmücker, 2021). They are therefore referred to here as **primary PoIs** or **Experience PoIs** (E-PoIs). They correspond to “attraction points” as they have been defined since the early 2000s. Since in the present context not only the points where the trip is *enjoyed* are relevant, we also include the points where tourists *have to* stay, in contrast to Padrón-Avila and Hernández-Martin (2022). These points can also be crowded with visitors. These PoIs are not attraction points, but merely help to facilitate the actual travel experience. Although they are visited by tourists, they are merely a means to an end. They fulfil all the characteristics of PoIs (locatable, geographically definable, accessible and visited by tourists) except for their inherent

attractiveness as points worth visiting. We therefore refer to them as **secondary PoIs** or **Functional PoIs** (F-PoIs). These include:

- Mobility infrastructure (e.g. car parks, access roads, airports),
- Service facilities (e.g. waste disposal for residential properties)
- Shopping facilities (e.g. supermarkets),
- Information points.

The following example illustrates the two categories: The Schleswig-Holstein Wadden Sea National Park is a trip-generating attraction for tourists. The beach in St. Peter-Ording, located in the Schleswig-Holstein Wadden Sea National Park (location of the E-PoI), is an experience point where many tourists stay to meet their needs such as bathing, recreation or experiencing nature (attractiveness of the E-PoI). In order to reach the beach, bus stops and parking spaces are needed (accessibility of the E-PoI). These can be considered as F-PoI, as they are visited by many guests, but are not attractive in the sense of generating experiences.

As shown above, the function of a place as a PoI is not solely dependent on its characteristics, but also on the characteristics of the users and the context. Thus, an airport may be an F-PoI in some cases (e.g. for departure on holiday) and an E-PoI in others (e.g. watching planes with children as part of a day trip). This argument can also be applied to other PoIs.

An E-PoI, e.g. a hiking trail, can also contain other E-PoIs (e.g. viewpoints) and F-PoIs (e.g. information boards).

Relationships between PoI and usage in digital visitor management systems

For measuring and influencing visitor flows, the constellation of E-PoI and F-PoI is relevant. Frequently, measurements are collected at an F-PoI (e.g. a car park at the beach) and used as an auxiliary variable (proxy) for the visitor numbers at an E-PoI (beach). For this, it is necessary that E-PoI and F-PoI are related to each other. The stronger this relationship is, the better the measurement at the F-PoI can be used as a proxy for the number of visitors at the E-PoI. The relationship must be determined concretely for each context, e.g. on the basis of attributes such as distances or the quantity of existing F-POI.

In the context of digital visitor management, it is a matter, among other things, of publishing (deploying) information about the (future) utilisation of PoI and the possible indication of alternatives in the case of too much visitor pressure (recommender). Here, the focus of the application and deployment is usually on the points of attraction (E-PoI). Based on the existing measuring stations in destinations (often at F-PoI), the recommender shows the existing secondary points of interest for each E-PoI. In case of a possible congestion of locations, another F-PoI for the same E-PoI (i.e. another car park for the beach) or even another point of attraction (e.g. another beach) can be displayed. These alternatives are usually based on attributes such as proximity to the original attraction point or category similarity (e.g. sandy beach).

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Notes

This document was produced as part of the project "AIR - AI-based Recommender for Sustainable Tourism" with partial funding from the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection.

For more information on AIR, please visit www.nit-kiel.de/air/.

Gefördert durch:

Bundesministerium
für Umwelt, Naturschutz, nukleare Sicherheit
und Verbraucherschutz

aufgrund eines Beschlusses
des Deutschen Bundestages

Suggested citation:

Reif, Julian; Schmücker, Dirk; Horster, Eric; Staubert, Tim (2023). *PoI –Points of Interest in Destinations*. (AIR Brief Reports). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7736822](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7736822)

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